

Preparation of some New 4-Arylhydrazone-pyrazolones and -pyrazoles†

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In continuation of our studies¹ on ethyl α -(4-alkoxy-2-nitro)phenylazo- β -oxobutyrate (1), we report here the results of the reaction of 1 with benzene sulphonyl hydrazide. Thus, condensation of 1 with benzenesulphonyl hydrazine in ethanol afforded the 1-phenylsulphonyl derivatives (2a, b). Their structures were confirmed by their correct analytical data, ir spectra, which showed bands at 1 690 and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=O and C=N), and the fact that treatment of 2a with alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave 3a and treatment of 3a with benzenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine at low temperature yielded 6a^{2,3} (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{NHNH}_2\cdot\text{EtOH}$, (ii) alc. KOH, H, (iii) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SO}_4$, NaOH, (iv) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{Cl}$, pyridine, (v) alc. KOH, H, (vi) CH_3O , MeOH, (vii) $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, H^+ .

Scheme 1

Methylation of 3a, b with dimethylsulphate gave 4 or 5, both consistent with the same empirical formula (Scheme 1). The ir spectra of the products showed bands at 3 250–3 200 (NH), 1 660–1 655

(C=O) and 1 600–1 595 cm^{-1} (C=N). Structure 5 was ruled out because it does not contain any carbonyl group.

The presence of the –CONH– linkage in 3 has prompted us to investigate its behaviour towards chlorosulphonation with benzenesulphonyl chloride. Thus, compounds 3a, b when heated with benzenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine gave the isomeric structure 6 rather than 2, as inferred from the disappearance of the carbonyl absorption band in their ir spectra. Further confirmation for the formation of 6a, b was gained upon treatment with alcoholic KOH to give 3.

It was reported that treatment of compounds 3 with formaldehyde in methanol afforded the *N*-hydroxymethyl derivatives (7)¹. When compounds 7 were treated with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, the *N*-methyl derivatives (8) were obtained. Their ir spectra showed bands at 1 600–1 650, 1 680–1 670 and 1 695–1 685 cm^{-1} , attributable to the amido, keto and the ester carbonyls, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Microanalyses of carbon and hydrogen were performed at Faculty of Science, University of Mansoura. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

1-Phenylsulphonyl-(4-alkoxy-2-nitro)phenylhydrazone-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2a, b): A mixture of the arylhydrazone derivatives¹ (1a, b; 0.01 mol) and benzenesulphonylhydrazide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h and set aside at room temperature overnight. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol: 2a (80%), $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$, m.p. 230°; 2b (85%), $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$, m.p. 185°.

Hydrolysis of 2a to (4-alkoxy-2-nitro)phenylhydrazone-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (3a): Compound 2a (0.5 g) was refluxed with 4% alcoholic KOH solution (10 ml) or pyridine (10 ml) for 1 h, then diluted with water and neutralised with HCl. The product proved to be 3a (m.p. and m.m.p.).

Conversion of 3a to 2a: To a solution of 3a (0.5 g) in pyridine (10 ml) cooled in an ice-bath, benzene sulphonylchloride (2 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. After stirring for 1 h, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and dried to give 2a (m.p. and m.m.p.).

1,3-Dimethyl-(4-alkoxy-2-nitro)phenylhydrazone-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (4a, b): Compounds 3a, b (0.01 mol) were heated with dimethyl sulphate (0.04 mol) for 5 min, cooled and poured onto ice-cold NaOH solution (30%). The resulting solids were crystallised from methanol: 4a (68%), $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4$, m.p. 190°; 4b (58%), $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4$, m.p. 171°.

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Conversion of 3 to 6 : To a suspension of **3a, b** (0.01 mol) in pyridine (15 ml), benzenesulphonyl chloride (0.012 mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then kept at room temperature for several hours and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solids were crystallised from ethyl alcohol: **6a** (63%), $C_{17}H_{15}N_5O_6S$, m.p. 190° ; **6b** (68%), $C_{18}H_{17}N_5O_6S$, m.p. 210° .

α -N-Methyl derivatives (8a, b) : To a cooled mixture of the *N*-hydroxymethyl derivatives¹ (**7a, b**; 1.0 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.0 ml), concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 ml) was added and then left to stand overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured onto ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: **8a** (55%), $C_{18}H_{21}N_5O_7$, m.p. 130° ; **8b** (64%), $C_{19}H_{23}N_5O_7$, m.p. 180° .

References

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1-(Substituted-anilinomalonyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-[substituted-azo]pyrazoles

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ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES have been shown to possess various biological activities¹. In view of tuberculostatic activity² of hydrazides and diverse biological activities of pyrazoles the synthesis of new pyrazoles has been accomplished.

Treatment of acetylacetone with different diazonium salts in presence of sodium acetate gave 2,4-diketo-3-(substituted-azo)pentanes (**3**), which on reaction with malonanilic acid hydrazides³ (**4**) in glacial acetic acid medium gave new 1-(substituted-anilinomalonyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-[substituted-azo]pyrazoles (**5**) (Scheme 1).

Biological activities : Potentialities of compounds **5f, k, l, p** and **s** were evaluated for *in vitro* anti-HIV activity under developmental therapeutic programme AIDS involving plating of susceptible human 'host' cells. The growth inhibitory response of **1f** was poor (15.30%) whereas that of **5k, l, p** and **s** was 39.79, 40.52, 34.23 and 39.78% respectively, at dose levels tested.

*B-24, Gandhi Nagar, Gwalior-474 002.

Scheme 1

Four compounds **5a, e, f** and **i** were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using species of *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *Diplococcus-pneumoniae*. None of the products showed activity against the bacteria at $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr.

2,4-Diketo(o-chlorophenylazo)pentane (3 ; R = Cl) : *o*-Chloroaniline (12.7 g, 0.1 mol) was dissolved in aqueous hydrochloric acid (80 ml; 1:1). The contents were stirred and cooled ($0-2^\circ$), and a cold solution of sodium nitrite (12.0 g in 30 ml water) was slowly added to it maintaining the temperature between 0 to 2° .

The cold diazotised solution was then added dropwise to a well-cooled and stirred mixture of acetylacetone (10 ml) and sodium acetate (8.0 g dissolved in 10 ml of 50% aqueous ethanol). Stirring was continued for 1.5 h and the resulting yellow crystals were washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.